

The quest for *in-situ* water pressure inside a hydrocarbon column

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In producing hydrocarbon reservoirs, the oil-water contact (OWC) continuously shifts as field development progresses, yet its exact position over time often remains uncertain. By monitoring pressure variations in both the oil and water phases, it is possible to estimate the distance to the OWC. Pressure data from production wells typically represent the highest recorded pressure, corresponding to the oil phase, while the pressure in the water phase remains unknown. Measuring the water phase pressure requires a method that selectively accesses the water phase (i.e. water film) within the reservoir rock. This study presents laboratory experiments performed with a hydrophilic probe to determine *in-situ* water pressure in pre-drained core plugs from Berea sandstone and Mons chalk outcrops to initial water saturations. The plugs were pre-drained under varying oil pressures using Isopar oil at ambient conditions. Additionally, some tests were conducted after aging at 80°C temperature with North Sea reservoir crude oil to achieve the desired wetting conditions. The tests on pre-drained chalk and sandstone plugs demonstrate that it is possible to use the hydrophilic probe to connect to the water film at oil overpressure of 8.0 bar. During the entire measurements, water production was monitored at the outlet end indicating that the water drainage process was continuing to an even lower water saturation while measuring the water pressure. Some of the laboratory experiments were interpreted using a numerical simulator to better understand the pressure and water saturation distribution during the water pressure measurements and to identify critical variables for reliable predications for field-scale applications. The pressure difference between oil and water provides valuable insights into the hydrocarbon column height in a newly discovered field. Detecting changes in the hydrocarbon – water pressure difference could serve as an early warning system for water approaching in the producing well. In addition, understanding the hydrocarbon column height can accelerate the appraisal processor guide infill drilling, reducing both costs and time. This, in turn, minimizes environmental impact by decreasing the number of wells required.

Introduction

In the discovery of a new hydrocarbon (HC) reservoir, the pressure of the HC phase (P_{HC}) as a function of depth can be easily measured in the well, or at the wall of the well, with current state of the art technology. However, the pressure of water phase (P_w), which is lower than P_{HC} above the free water level (FWL), must be measured inside the reservoir rock by a method that ensures a continuous contact with the water phase. The measurement should be done beyond the invaded zone to avoid disturbances of water distribution from mud invasion during drilling. In addition, the reservoir formation high above FWL will normally have high oil saturation, and low water saturation (S_{wi}). Water saturation can be as low as 5-10% for very good quality reservoir rock (Darcy range), and higher (20-30%) with less good reservoir rock properties (mDarcy range). At high pressure difference between the oil and water phases, the water mobility becomes very low and it could be time consuming to measure the water pressure correctly. It is therefore not a trivial task to measure the representative P_w for reliable FWL calculations. In most hydrocarbon reservoirs the water phase is likely to be continuous even at a very low water saturation and at a significant hydrocarbon overpressure. This is because of the polar nature of the water molecule and the polarity in the surface of the minerals in the reservoir: Water sticks to the

surface of the reservoir grains. Given enough time the pressure gradient through this thin film of water becomes the same as if the water was in bulk or can be extrapolated (**Fig. 1**). By measuring both the water and the hydrocarbon pressure at a given depth inside a hydrocarbon reservoir it is possible to estimate the vertical distance down to the free-water level. The oil/water contact (OWC) will be immediately above the FWL only separated by the threshold pressure of the formation.

Figure 1: Current art: pressure measurements at multiple depths defining the FWL, new art: pressure measurements. at a single depth. Density of the fluids are used to extrapolate the pressure trends down to the FWL.

The only additional information needed are the densities of the fluids. The pressure difference between oil and water could provide valuable information about the hydrocarbon column height of a new discovery. In some cases, the OWC cannot be estimated from either a saturation log or from a traditional pressure versus depth

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plot. Knowledge about the hydrocarbon column height could also speed up the appraisal process, or guide infill drilling, saving time and money.

Detecting changes in the hydrocarbon – water pressure difference could work as an early warning system for water approaching a field in production. The environmental impact will be reduced because fewer wells will have to be drilled (Rolfsvåg et.al. 2019).

Previous researchers have developed multiphase cell set-ups where oil and water pressures were controlled independently. Lackner and Torsæter (2005) proposed a direct method for measuring dynamic phase pressures for water and oil. The method provided dynamic capillary pressure on core plugs in the laboratory by individual phase pressure measurement along the lines proposed in the current project. Capotosto et. al (2021) used a similar probe prototype to validate at laboratory scale via measurements of water pressure in plugs saturated with water and oil. Tests on sandstone plugs show that the probe can successfully measure water pressure as long as the water phase is continuous in the pore space.

Objective

In this work, the main objective was to use a test rig to measure the *in-situ* water pressure in different rock materials at ambient conditions.

Scope of work

The effect of the following parameters were investigated through laboratory and simulation experiments:

- Hydrophilic probe design for P_w and resistivity (R_w) at various water saturations (pre-established, i.e. primary drainage, or varied during the experiment from the “outlet-side” through the porous plate).
- Rock types (sandstone and chalk) with mineralogy and petrophysical properties (permeability and porosity).
- Different fluids; synthetic formation water, laboratory oil and reservoir crude oil.
- Interpretate the laboratory experiments to gain an understanding of the long-term drainage process in a porous plate setup and identify variables critical for fast measurement of reliable *in-situ* water pressure with the hydrophilic probe
- Demonstrate what can be simulated with existing simulation tools and identify what is missing with respect to simulating laboratory scale experiments and act as support in field scale implementations.

The Hydrophilic test rig

The Hydrophilic test rig is as shown in Fig.2 it consists of two main parts, a chamber for the plug which can take plug samples up to 10 cm in diameter and length. The probe is fitted with a pressure gauge for water pressure and is in contact with the plug. The probe can be placed on various places on the surface of the plug by using the movable probe arm and chamber relative to one another. A separate pressure gauge was used to monitor the oil pressure. A two electrode resistivity meter was used for resistivity measurements across the plug. A schematic of

the rig is illustrated in Fig.3. The plug sample will be surrounded by oil on all sides except at the outlet end which is attached to a water-wet ceramic disc as porous plate. The outlet end of the plug sample has good contact with the ceramic disc to allow only water to be drained from the plug sample. Kaolin paste is used to ensure the continuity at the outlet end.

Figure 2: Hydrophilic test rig design and probe tip

Figure 3: Simple schematic of the test rig. Resistivity was measured across the plug

Rock material

Rock types (sandstone and chalk) with different mineralogy and petrophysical properties (permeability and porosity) were selected. Two outcrops were used, Berea Sandstone and Mons Chalk. The Chalk plug was represented by an outcrop chalk, Mons from the Mons quarry in Belgium. Prior to the tests, the plugs were characterized by measuring the petrophysical properties, gas permeability and porosity at ambient conditions. 5 plugs of each rock type with a constant diameter of 1.5 inch and length of approximately 7.0-8.0 cm were used.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analyses of Berea sandstone and Mons chalk are shown in Fig.4-5. As shown in Fig. 4, typical Berea sandstone is dominated by

quartz and contains significant amounts of different clay types. K-feldspar is abundant; carbonate (often as cement) is common. Rutile is a minor component. gypsum and halite can be found. In **Fig.5** Mons chalk is characterized with high specific surface area. BET analyses measured on end-trimmed samples for Berea sandstone ranged between 0.57 – 0.84 m²/g and 2.0 m²/g for Mons chalk.

Figure 4: SEM micrograph of Berea sandstone (at 200µm and Mag 150x)

Figure 5: SEM micrograph of Mons chalk at 1µm and Mag 12.4k times.

Methodology

General rig-operating procedure

The fully saturated (or pre-drained) plug is mounted on a support attached to the inlet piece of the chamber (Fig.1). To enable accurate measurement of the water pressure, the plug must be in contact with the fully synthetic formation water (SFW) saturated porous plate at the outlet. A layer of kaolin paste (about 0.32g with about 0.12 ml SFW) is applied as contact medium to ensure water continuity between the plug and plate. The moist kaolin paste is smeared onto the ceramic disk before mounting the outlet piece to the chamber. For tests performed at 100% water saturation; after measuring the gas permeability, the plug is first saturated with synthetic formation water (SFW) using vacuum overnight. Pre-drained plugs were prepared by mounting the 100% water saturated plugs in core holders and drained using the porous plate at different oil pressures. The composition of SFW is as shown in *Table 1*.

The probe assembly is vacuumed, and water-saturated disc is mounted to the probe under water. Afterwards, a suitable amount of paste is applied on the disc. The probe is gradually lowered until a short distance (few millimeters) to the surface of the plug.

The plug and outlet piece are mounted in the chamber (Fig 1). The chamber is filled with test fluid; Isopar H or reservoir crude oil.

Table 1 : Synthetic formation water

Salt	(SFW), [g/l]
NaCl	36.81
KCl	0.31
MgCl ₂ *6H ₂ O	4.48
CaCl ₂ *2H ₂ O	33.25

The oil pressure is ramped up to the desired pressure. The probe is lowered gradually to touch the surface of the plug (See Fig.3) for the water pressure measurements.

When preparing for a Touch Down (TD), the probe is lifted above the ball valve and the oil chamber is isolated. The ceramic disk at the tip of the probe is cleaned with SFW and fresh paste is applied, and the probe is remounted. The response time based on the amount of paste applied was also investigated during the last two TDs.

Experimental results

Test#1; Berea_134, 100% water saturation

In Test#1, the aim was to perform an oil-water drainage process while monitoring the in-situ pressure of the water phase in a 100% water saturated Berea sandstone plug. *Table 2* show the plug dimensions and properties, dry and saturated weight after the drainage process. Water saturation (S_w) is calculated based on the weight of the plug after the drainage process and the known density of oil and water. Dean Stark distillation has been used to control the end-point water saturation (*S_w). End-point water saturation (**S_w) based on Dean stark show an acceptable agreement between calculated end-point saturation with a variation of 3% points (~10% in uncertainty).

Table 2: Test #1, plug properties and end-point water saturations prior to and after the tests

D	L	Dry Wt.	PV	Porosity	Wt. after drainage	*S _w	**S _w
(cm)	(cm)	(g)	(ml)	(frac)	(g)	(frac)	(frac)
3.70	8.60	209.3	13.5	0.146	220.8	0.290	0.320

The following test protocol was used:

- Experiment allowed to continue for a few days at 1 bar oil pressure P_o in the test chamber
- Wait until P_w in the core plug is < 200 mbar.
- Increase P_o to 4000 mbar
- Wait a couple of days, until P_w has fallen back < 200 mbar
- Lift the probe – wait for a few minutes – lower it back in the same spot and wait for stability of P_w

Fig.6 show the oil and water pressure, and resistivity profiles measured as function of time. A decline in water pressure and increase in resistivity at a constant oil pressure of 1.0 bar.

As shown in the fig, there is linearity in water pressure (P_w) versus time in the first part and a non-linearity in the last part. In the linear part, P_w declined at -134 mbar/day and reaching less than 0.2 bar after a week. The drop in water pressure (P_w) is as expected but the linear behaviour as a function of time towards the end of the drainage process is not yet properly understood. The mobility of water in the plug containing oil at higher pressure is low, but not zero. The mobility of water will – with time bring the system to static equilibrium.

Figure 6: Test #1, oil-water drainage, Berea sandstone plug showing water pressure and resistivity as a function of time at oil pressure of 1.0 bar.

Fig. 7 shows P_w and resistivity profiles at oil pressure of 4.0 bar. When the oil pressure is increased, there is a sudden jump in resistivity to a level almost three times higher than observed at $P_o=1$ bar, followed by a gradual increase due to drainage of water from the plug. In the same period, there is a linear decline in P_w with -203 mbar per day down to a P_w of about 2.1 bar.

Figure 7: Test #1, oil-water drainage, Berea sandstone plug with water pressure and resistivity profiles with time at oil pressure of 4.0 bar.

A sharp increase in P_w and resistivity is observed when the probe was lifted and lowered back to the same position on the plug after a few minutes. The increase in P_w is as expected, due to the increase in oil pressure, however P_w did not decline as expected after TD. This could be due to poor contact between the probe tip and plug surface.

Test#2; Berea_145, 100% water saturation

In Test #2, the following objectives were aimed:

- to demonstrate the drainage process on a Berea core sample and perform a few touch downs (TDs) at similar oil pressure conditions to observe the water pressure response behaviour and time recorded by the probe as performed in Test #1.

Test#2 was performed at oil pressure of 1.0 bar. Table 3 shows the plug properties, and calculated end-point water saturation estimated at the end of the test. Dean stark distillation has been used to confirm the end-point water saturation.

Table 3: Test#2 Berea Sandstone plug properties including end-point water saturations

D	L	Dry	PV	Porosity	Wt. After	*Sw	**Sw
0	0	weight	(ml)	(frac)	drainage	(frac)	(frac)
(cm)	(cm)	(g)			(g)		
3.70	6.77	155.1	10.9	0.145	167.5	0.255	0.220

Fig.8 shows the oil pressure, water pressure and resistivity profiles measured with time. In this test, the drainage process was started at an oil pressure of 1.0 bar, water pressure decreases with a corresponding increase in resistivity as expected. As the drainage process went on, there is a gradual decrease in the water pressure to approximately 1.0 bar pressure difference with oil pressure. During the test, the probe was lifted and taken out to perform a new touch down and fresh Kaolinite paste was applied for the TD.

Figure 8: Test#2, Berea sandstone with touch down $P_o=1.0$ bar, probe pressure gradually gets back on the same decline trend as observed after first TD. The spike in pressure profiles are due taking the probe in and out of the test chamber

At TD water pressure showed to follow a similar decline trend of -136 mbar/day observed in earlier test, as shown in the figure. Following the test at 1.0 bar oil pressure. The figure shows a slight water pressure increases to keep the same approximate pressure difference with oil pressure, water pressure shows a gradual decreasing trend that can be a sign of the ongoing drainage process after the TD.

Test #3, Pre-drained Mons Chalk_202

In test#3, a pre-drained Mons chalk outcrop plug was used. Table 4 shows the plug properties including the initial water saturation pre-drained at 4.5 bar oil pressure and at the end of the test at 8.0 bar oil pressure with Isopar H. In this test, about 0.32 g of ~40% water-content moist paste was used at the tip of the probe.

Fig.9 show the measured P_w and R_w profiles during the test. During the first TD, the probe was lowered to about a centimeter distance of the plug, the oil pressure in the chamber was ramped up to about 1 bar.

Table 4: Test#3, Mons plug properties including end-point water saturations

D	L	k_g	PV	Porosity	wt. after drainage	* S_w	** S_w
(cm)	(cm)	(mD)	(ml)	(frac)	(g)	(frac)	(frac)
3.7	6.8	1.5	29.3	0.382	150.1	0.255	0.136

During this period the probe P_w also followed the same trend showing that the paste has enough water to be responsive to the increased oil pressure. Afterwards, the probe was lowered gradually to touch the surface of the plug once the oil pressure reached about 4.5 bar (Fig.9).

Figure 9: Test#3, Mons Chalk plug with water pressure and resistivity profiles at 5 and 8 bar oil pressures, and positions of TDs.

When the probe touches the plug’s surface, there is a significant drop of P_w an indication that the small amount of water in paste on the tip of probe is quickly adsorbed by the pre-drained core plug. The test is continued for about one day at $P_o = 5$ bar and P_w declines to 3.65 bar, i.e. approximately 1.4 bar difference with oil pressure. Afterwards, the oil pressure is increased to 8 bar with a sudden increase in P_w and stabilizes at about 5 bar. The second TD was performed at 8 bar P_o when the oil/water pressure difference had increased to about 3.2 bar after 3 days. Fresh paste of approximately same amount was applied and TD2 was performed. As shown in the Figure, a probe lost connectivity three days after the second TD at an oil – water pressure difference of approximately 3.8 bar, and the probe pressure increased to the same value as the oil pressure.

Test #4, Pre-drained Mons Chalk_205

The test was performed at the same oil pressure used in the pre-drainage of the plug, 5 bar with Isopar H and water production was not measured. The test was used to determine the time for measurement of P_w (equilibration time). This is mainly decided by water mobility from the plug to the probe tip, and the compressibility of the water volume between probe tip and pressure gauge. As shown in Fig.10. Both probe tip volume and amount of water on the probe tip influence the measured probe water pressures (Fig.11). The measurements are consistent and

show a pressure difference of 4.85 bar depending on the amount of water used. Note that “peaks” observed in the figures in the initial periods could be a useful indication for TD when visual inspection is not possible, e.g., in the field. The reason for the peak is as follows: The pressure in the probe tip holder is increased to approximately one bar above oil pressure before the TD so that some water is pressed onto the probe tip.

Figure 10: Test#4, Measured water pressures at 5 bar oil pressure with Probe tip #134 made by the old method with the ceramic locked in fixed position whereas the new probe tips (#14-2&26672-2) were made by a new method with a sleeve surrounding the ceramic plate

This pressurizing causes the probe tip to move slightly “outwards”. Thus, the tip will be pressed “inwards” during TD, causing a pressure peak. The compressed water inside the probe tip holder must then be produced through the tip into the core for equilibration. This extra pressure and water may to some degree delay the equilibration towards water phase in the plug, as shown in the figure.

Figure 11: Test#4 for Mons chalk zoomed in for 0- 0.8 hours with dates at different touch downs with varying amount of water used.

As shown in the Fig. 10&11, the equilibration time for measurement of stable water pressure depends on volume of water in the probe tip holder (compressibility) and amount of water on the probe tip. Laboratory results show that water volume should be minimized, both in the probe tip holder and on the surface of the tip, for most rapid equilibration time.

Tests with reservoir crude oil (STO)

In this section, results from experiments with STO after ageing are presented. The plugs pre-drained with Isopar H. The Berea sandstone plugs except the Mons chalk were

pre-drained at 5 bar pressure using laboratory oil (Isopar H) and later aged with filtered STO at 80°C for 3 weeks. The Mons chalk was drained at 6 bar. The plugs were tested with laboratory oil for water pressure measurements in the Hydrophilic rig at the same oil pressure drainage pressure before testing with STO after ageing. There was a significant shift in resistivities for the Mons Chalk (1.90 to 5.71 kohm) but not the Berea Sandstone (5.02 to 5.30 kohm) plugs after ageing at 80°C.

Test #5, Berea_ with lab oil and STO

In Test#5, Berea plug was first tested with Isopar H followed by STO after ageing at 80°C. The plug was drained to an S_{wi} of less than 20%, prior to the test with Isopar H, however resistivity data show that the ageing process may have had very little effect (based on R_w of 5.02 to 5.3 kohm) on wettability of the plug. **Fig.12** shows the measured *in-situ* P_w and R_w profiles with time.

Figure 12: Test#5, measured water pressure and resistivity profiles with time, and comparison before and after ageing with STO at ambient

The shapes of the P_w profiles look quite different; the slopes and the final end-point values differ. P_w with lab oil stabilizes at less than 1.0 bar and above 1.0 bar with STO. The difference could be due to the nature of the water film after ageing with STO, continuous water film after drainage with Isopar H and discontinuous phase after ageing with STO.

Test #6, Mons Chalk_201 Lab oil and STO

Fig. 13 shows the results for the test with Mons chalk plug using Isopar H oil at 6 bar oil pressure and after ageing with STO. In the presence of Isopar H, the probe shows a sudden decrease in water pressure, P_w within the first 4-5 hours and gradual increase in water pressure.

After ageing, electrical resistivity showed a clear shift in resistivity values, a confirmation that the expected change in wettability occurred during the ageing process.

This is due to the closing of the outlet valve during the period within 10 – 30 hours but the P_w starts to decrease again when the outlet valve is opened again. In the presence of STO, there is similar trend in P_w , but P_w seems to stabilise after about 20 hours.

At TD on the aged plug, the water pressure stabilizes at about 3.6 bar. After probe pressure stabilization, the core

outlet was closed, and water pressure was adjusted to 3.5 bar and push was applied to the probe against the plug.

Figure 13: Test#6, Mons Chalk, comparison of water pressure and resistivities profiles with lab Oil and after ageing with STO

Simulation, some selected laboratory experiments

This section presents an attempt to simulate the experiments on measuring the *in-situ* water pressure in drained core plugs. We test how simulations can improve interpretation of experiments and try to identify mechanisms that are important for the process. An overview of selected experiments used in the simulations are given Table 5.

The simulations are done with IORCoresim developed within the National Improved Oil recovery (IOR) Centre. This simulator has appropriate grid options and flexible boundary conditions that allows easy modelling of the porous plate type experiments.

Theory

Two-phase flow in a porous medium is described by combining Darcy's law:

$$\mathbf{u}_l = -\frac{\mathbf{K}k_{r,l}}{\mu_l} \cdot (\nabla p_l - \rho_l \mathbf{g}), \quad l = w, o \quad (1)$$

and mass conservation:

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho_l \mathbf{u}_l) + \dot{m}_l = -\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\phi S_l \rho_l), \quad l = w, o \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{u}_l is the phase flow velocity vector, \mathbf{K} is the absolute permeability tensor, $k_{r,l}$ the relative permeability, \mathbf{g} the gravity vector, ρ_l the phase density, \dot{m}_l a source term in terms mass flow rate per unit volume, ϕ the porosity and S_l the phase l saturation.

For a two-phase system (e.g., water and oil), the relative permeabilities are generally considered plug properties depending on the pore geometry, rock wettability and saturation history. The rock's effective wettability will in general depend on the rock mineralogy, adsorption of polar species on the rock surface, which in turn depends on the oil saturation, and on composition of the brine and oil. In particular, the presence of polar species (basic or acidic) in the oil are important. Ideally, the saturation functions should be measured at conditions representative

for the relevant process (drainage (decreasing S_w) or imbibition (increasing S_w)).

In the experiments that we want to simulate, the saturation functions are unknowns. We therefore select relative permeability from the literature obtained on similar material as initial guess and tune the curves to be consistent with available data measured in the lab. To ease the tuning process a suitable formula is selected for representing the relative permeability functions (LET function):^[1]

$$k_{rl} = k_{rle} \frac{S_{ln}^{L_l}}{S_{ln}^{L_l + E_l(1-S_{ln})^{T_l}}}, \quad S_{ln} = \frac{S_l - S_{lr}}{1 - S_{wr} - S_{or}}, \quad l = w, o. \quad (3)$$

To represent the ‘‘capillary’’ pressure, we use a variant of the Skjæveland correlation^[2] and assume J -scaling which is considered reasonable for primary drainage curves on cores of similar rock types:

$$J = \frac{C_L}{(S_w - S_L)^{E_L}} - \frac{C_R}{(S_R - S_w)^{E_R}} + C_0, \quad (4)$$

$$"p_c" = IFT \cdot \sqrt{\frac{k}{\phi}} \cdot J. \quad (5)$$

Selected lab experiments

Experiments used in the simulations, and relevant plug properties are listed in Table 5. The pore volume (PV) and permeability of Tests#1, #5 and #6, which are pre-drained by the porous plate method in core holders, were measured with N_2 at a net confinement pressure of 20 bar. Fluid properties used in the simulations are given in Table 6.

The different experiments were simulated using radial 2D or 3D models for the experiments conducted in the Hydrophilic test cell. The use of 3D models was needed to model fluid exchange between the probe located at the core surface and the plug.

Table 5 : Plug data, selected simulated experiments

Test and Core ID	L (cm)	D (cm)	PV (cm ³)	Porosity (vol.frac.)	k (mD)	Experiment
Test#1 (Berea 124)	8.600	3.7	14.06	0.1520	25	Primary drainage with probe
Test#5 (Berea 234)	7.088	3.706	13.07	0.1709	117	Pre-drainage porous plate TD on pre-drained core (Isopar H)
Test#6 (Mons 201)	7.053	3.72	28.74	0.3749	1.67	Pre-drainage porous plate TD on pre-drained plug

The 2D and 3D core models were gridded with (15×1×40) and (15×8×40) or (15×6×40) cells. The gridding in the radial direction (15 cells) was done so that all cells have equal volume. In angular direction, the three first cells were 10°, while the remaining cells were summed up to 150°, so that half the plug (180°) was modelled. An additional 6 layers were used, whereof 5 layers represented the disk, and one single thin layer acted as

boundary layer between the core and the disk to reduce numerical errors. The porous disk properties used in simulations of the two different experimental setups are given in Table 7. In addition, an entry pressure high enough to prevent oil entering was assigned to the probe cells.

Table 6 : Fluid properties used in the simulations

Fluid type	Viscosity (mPa·s)	Density (g/ml)	IFT (mN/m)
Brine	1.02	1.000	
Isopar H	1.13	0.759	45

Table 7: Porous disc properties

	Thickness (cm)	Porosity (frac)	Permeability (mD)
Pre-drainage in core-holder	0.635	0.32	0.0026
Porous disc cell	0.750	0.32	0.05

Berea Sandstone

Porous plate drainage Test#1 (Berea_124)

The results from pre-drainage of plugs, performed before the P_w measurements with probe at low water saturations, were utilized in the simulations to tune the saturation functions and the tail of the relative permeability to water. The pre-drainage was carried out in core holders with a net overburden pressure of 20 bar. The plugs were drained with a white oil (Isopar H). The oil pressure is stepwise increased each time the drained water production rate approaches zero, up to 5 bar.

Fig. 14 shows the experimental data plotted with oil over pressure on the y-axis and average S_w on the x-axis. In the right of Fig. 14, the simulated relation, P_o versus S_w , compares well with the experimental data, but with some deviations. These deviations are partly explained by non-monotonic water production

Figure 14: Experimental relation between applied oil pressure and experimental S_w plotted together with applied oil-water pressure function (left figure) and corresponding simulated results (right figure), primary drainage of Test#1_Berea_124.

The low water mobility encountered in the drainage process is represented by the tail of the relative permeability plotted on logarithmic scale in Fig.15 The relative permeability used in the simulation are compared to other primary drainage data obtained for Berea from the literature.

Beside the k_{rw} -tail, the main input to the simulations is the P_c versus saturation curve. As a starting point we used a primary drainage curve obtained from mercury injection

in a 500 mD Berea plug and converted the data to dimensionless form (J-function) using Eq. (4). The results fitted to Eq. (5) was then tuned to be consistent with the available experimental results for Test#1 (Berea 124). The final curve is plotted together with the original curve in the left of Fig.15.

Figure 15: Saturation functions used for simulation of the Test#1 case (Berea 124). Left: primary drainage (dimensionless J-function) from Hg-injection curve used in the simulation (J-m). Right: relative permeability used (-m) plotted together with curves from the literature.

During the P_w measurement for Test#1, the plug (Berea) was done with a probe attached to the plug’s surface from the start. The test was carried out with an oil pressure of 1 bar for one week, before the oil pressure was increased to 4 bar. The experiment was first simulated with a 2D radial model representing half the plug as can be seen in Fig.16. Fig.16 shows the simulated development within the plug in the early phase of the experiment. Initially, oil enters the plug from all sides exposed to oil.

Figure 16: Primary drainage Test#1 (Berea). Simulated distribution of S_o (top row), $P_o - P_w$ (middle row) and P_w (bottom row) in the early phase of the experiment at $t = 0.03$ days (left column) and 0.3 days (right column)

When the oil reaches the water wet disc, it will stop while water is still being drained out from the end of the plug due to the lower pressure at the disc outlet side. As a result, oil accumulates to a higher saturation at the end of

the plug. This is clearly seen in Fig.16 at $t=0.3$ days. At this point, the flow pattern has become fully linear in the plug length direction. The saturation gradient within the plug results in a gradient in water pressure, which in turn is the driving force for water flowing from all parts of the core towards the water-wet disk.

The production mechanism for the porous plate method is further illustrated in Fig.17 showing profiles of phase pressures and saturation through the plug and the porous disk. After the first invasion period, the oil pressure becomes almost constant due to low rate and high oil mobility. Water being drained out through the disk from the end of the plug results in a saturation gradient with decreasing S_w towards the disk.

Figure 17: Simulated pressure and saturation profiles through Test#1_Berea and outlet disk (shaded area on the right) at $t = 0.3$ days.

Further development of the saturation and water pressure profiles during the first five days of drainage are plotted in Fig.18. The development of the water pressure profiles contains important information regarding modelling the porous plate drainage process. At the early stage, most of the pressure drop is over the porous disk, while at later stages essentially all of the pressure drop takes place within the plug.

From Fig.18, we know that the oil pressure is practically constant. From this we conclude that the drainage history does not depend on the oil relative permeability or oil viscosity, within some limits. The simulated pressure, saturation electrical resistance history are compared with experimental results in Fig. 19 and Fig. 20. However, the experimental saturation history is estimated and follows the same trend as measured.

Furthermore, the drainage is insensitive to the part of the curve high water saturation of the water relative permeability, while the lower part (k_{rw} -tail) plays a dominating role.

Thus, history matching of the experiments to tune saturation functions should only be used for the k_{rw} -tail. It will help using a high permeability disc because that will increase the influence of k_{rw} . A disk permeability of 0.05 mD was used in the simulations for this experiment.

Water pressure representing different parts of the plug is obtained by printing out block values from the inlet end, the centre of the core and from the outlet end. The outermost block at the radial surface is used.

The probe is assumed to be located approximately at the centre of the plug and the corresponding simulated water pressure is denoted “mid P_w ” in Fig.19. Also shown in the

figure are P_w from the core inlet and outlet ends and the volume weighted average for the core, $\langle P_w \rangle$.

To test out possible probe behaviour, we vary the permeability, porosity and compressibility of the probe region. By default, IORCoresim uses the oil pressure to calculate compression, but that can be altered to using the water pressure instead. We also include an option to change the net overburden pressure during the simulation. The pore volume of a grid cell is now computed:

$$V_p = V_{p0} \cdot \exp\left((p_w - p_{ref} - dp_{ob}) \cdot c_r\right) \quad (6)$$

where dp_{ob} is the change in net overburden pressure compared to reference conditions, V_{p0} the pore volume at reference pressure p_{ref} and c_r the rock compressibility. The simulation of Test#1 (Berea) is now repeated using a high compressibility, $c_r=0.1 \text{ bar}^{-1}$ for the probe grid cells. The water saturated core is initialized at 1 bar. As p_w decreases, the probe pore volume decreases and water is expelled from the probe into the core. When increasing p_o from 1 to 4 bar, dp_{ob} is set to 3 bar (initially $dp_{ob}=0$), which results in a corresponding jump in p_w within the probe.

Figure 18: Simulated saturation and water pressure profiles through Test#1 Beria_124 at different times during drainage with 1 bar oil pressure.

Fig. 19 shows results from the repeated simulations including an approximate probe representation. The simulated probe pressure and $P_{w,mid}$ are from the same position at the plug surface, but on opposite radial sides. The delayed probe pressure response is only partially captured in the first period with $P_o=1$ bar, while after increasing P_o to 4 bar the probe pressure is easily reproduced. Initially in the first period, the flow from the probe is restricted only by the conductivity of the probe. In the second period, the average water saturation in the core is below 0.35 (see Fig. 20) and kr_w below 10^{-4} , and

the water exchange with the probe is becoming increasingly restricted by the low water mobility in the volume surrounding the probe.

The simulated volume exchange between plug and probe (dV_{probe}) for Test#1 was 0.0015 ml in the first period ($P_o=1$ bar) which increased to 0.0020 ml in the second period. These number corresponds 0.00021 and 0.00029 saturation units of the plug.

Figure 19: Primary drainage of Test#1 (Berea) with probe, experimental probe pressure and simulated water pressure from different locations in core, at the core inlet (P_w in), plug midst (P_w mid), the core outlet (P_w out) and averaged water pressure for the core ($\langle P_w \rangle$). Simulated electrical resistance over the core is plotted on the right axis (Z12)

Figure 20: Saturation and electrical resistance in the Test#1 drainage, experimental and simulated. Note: experimental saturation data are approximate.

Test#5_Berea_234 with Isopar H

Fig.21 shows experimental and simulated probe pressure after a probe touchdown on Test#5 (Berea 234). This plug is pre-drained in the same way as Test#6 (Berea 124) presented above, with 5 bar oil pressure using Isopar H.

The probe pressure in Fig.21 deviates from the previous plug by levelling out at a P_w of approximately 0.8 bar, while less than 0.1 bar was observed for Test#5. The different behaviour was modelled mainly by adjusting the oil over pressure to 4.3 bar at initial S_w .

Fig.22 shows simulated saturation, oil over pressure and water pressure distribution in a cut through half the plug, 10 hours after the TD. Initial S_w in the plug was 0.128. The upper figure shows a small but marked decrease in S_w inside the plug close to the outlet disk, and a small increase in S_w in the area surrounding the probe. The injected water from the probe's paste inflates the water pressure locally and is the driving force for the spreading of the introduced water to remote parts of the plug.

The resulting water pressure gradient is a P_w decreasing away from the probe. The speed of the water spreading process depends on the water mobility on the slope of the saturation curve and the saturation range just above the disturbed S_w (which in this case is 0.128). If the spreading within the plug is fast, due to high water mobility, then the time required for water exchange between the probe and the plug will be sensitive to the probe conductivity.

Figure 21: Simulated pressure profiles with TD on Test#5 (Berea_234) pre-drained with white oil (Isopar H).

Figure 22: Simulated water saturation, oil/water pressure variations and water pressure distributions 10 hours after the probe touchdown. Note: upper cut-off values have been used, and red areas indicates values \geq the maximum value in the legends. Initial S_w in the plug was 0.128. Test#5 (Berea 234).

In the present case with low water mobility (k_{rw} less than 10^{-7} at $S_w=0.128$), most of the pressure drop between probe and the core take place inside the plug (bottom part of Fig.19). Main assumptions for this plug; low k_{rw} delays spreading of water from the probe and further drainage through the outlet porous disc is slow.

Test#6 (Mons_201) with Isopar H

Results from the pre-drainage of Test#6 (Mons 201), simulated and experimental, are presented in Fig. 23 and Fig. 24. Fig. 23 summarizes the drainage in a plot of applied oil pressure plotted versus saturation. The figure

shows the amount produced at each step, and the final saturation at each pressure step before p_o is increased. The oil over pressure used in the simulation is plotted on top of the data in the left of Fig. 23, while on the right-hand side corresponding simulated are plotted with the experimental data.

The relative permeability functions used and the oil over pressure on dimensionless form (J-function) are shown in Fig. 24. The denoted J-m1 is used in the pre-drainage, J-m2 is used in the probe touchdown simulations presented in the next chapter. Also shown in the figure is a J-function obtained from mercury injection for Mons chalk.

Figure 23: Experimental relation between applied oil pressure and experimental S_w plotted together with applied oil over pressure function (left figure) and corresponding simulated results (right figure), primary drainage of Test#6_Mons_201.

Figure 24: Saturation functions for Test#6 (Mons 201)

Results from the probe touchdown on the Mons chalk pre-drained with Isopar H at $P_o=6$ bar is shown in Fig.25. The outlet end is initially closed at a disk pressure of 0.6 bar. The disk pressure increased further and converged with the probe pressure at a stable level of approximately 1.7 bar. After 23 hours, the outlet end is opened, and the probe pressure starts to decrease at a slow linear rate.

Figure 25: Touchdown on Test#6 (Mons 201) pre-drained with white oil (Isopar H).

One may observe that in the first period with closed outlet, the probe pressure goes through a minimum which is

lower than the disk pressure and then increases slowly towards the disk pressure.

The stable level of 1.7 bar for both the disc and probe pressure is significantly higher than expected based on the results from the pre-drainage. To achieve similar results in the simulation, the oil over pressure had to be reduced significantly. Thus, increasing the water saturation from the experimental value 0.105 to 0.150.

Figure 26: Simulated water pressure distribution in pre-drained chalk 20 hours after probe touchdown, Test#6 (Mons 201).

This reproduced the observed water pressure level. The observed behaviour of the probe pressure going through a minimum below the disk pressure could not be simulated. After 20 hours, the simulated probe pressure was still slightly higher than the disk pressure as can be seen in Fig.26. The simulated decline in probe pressure after opening the outlet (Fig.26) is slower than observed in the experiment.

Discussion

The identification of the Oil/Water Contact (OWC) in a hydrocarbon reservoir is crucial for the determination of its volume and it is also important for detailed petrophysical calculations. Estimation of the OWC requires the determination of the Free Water Level (FWL). Laboratory tests have been used to measure the water pressure in water-oil saturated samples for continuous water phase in pore space. The simulation work presented in this report represents a first attempt on simulating experiments related to measurement of in-situ the water pressure with a hydrophilic probe. The focus has been on increasing the understanding of involved mechanisms and identify unresolved issues. Less effort has been spent on exact matching, partly because the available experiments contain insufficient information to uniquely determine the model parameters, and secondly because the work was done within a limited timeframe.

The saturation functions were primarily generated from the primary drainage starting at 100% water saturation, but also tuned to be consistent with water pressures measured by the probe on the pre-drained cores and probe pressure decline rates after probe touchdowns.

The preliminary representation of the hydrophilic probe by assigning special properties to some grid cells at the core boundary, seems to have captured the observed probe behaviour quite well. There are three important properties of probe; it has a volume filled with water, a compressibility and a conductivity. The probe water volume and its compressibility define how much water must flow out of or into the probe due to a pressure change. The flow of water from the probe into the core is restricted by both the probe conductivity (kpr) and by the core's water mobility.

Atypical amount of kaolin paste used with the probe is 0.3 g, and that the water content in the paste is 42.3 wt%. This indicates a water volume of 0.12 ml in the compressible paste, which is 2 to 5 times the probe volume used in the simulations. Further experiments that can restrict the models are measurement of the paste compressibility and its conductivity. Another observation regarding the probe pressure measurements on pre-drained cores deserves some attention. Only for Test#1 (Berea 124) was the probe pressure in line with the pre-drainage history, while for Test#5 (Berea 234) and Test#6 (Mons 201), the probe pressure declines towards levels higher than expected. For the Mons chalk case, this behaviour may have been triggered by hysteresis effects, due to probe water inflow and enforced by additional water originating from increasing the disk pressure to 0.6 bar and closing the outlet. Hysteresis options are currently not available in the IORCoreSim simulator.

Conclusions

Based on the laboratory experiments and simulations, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The work presents and validates a probe for measuring the water pressure in oil saturated plugs. The probe offers the possibility of measuring the water pressure in porous media independently of the oil pressure for the case where oil and water are both present in the pore space.
- It has been demonstrated that the water pressure in the presence of over-pressured oil, and at low water saturation can be measured in both Sandstone and Chalk plugs and also in the presence of oil after ageing
- An accurate measurement of the thin water film pressure can be done in minutes (less than an hour) after the probe touches the surface of the plug sample in most cases. Simulation results indicate that the driving force for production of water from the plug towards the disc is water pressure gradient (oil pressure is ~constant)
- For a reservoir in pressure equilibrium, with a continuous water phase, the vertical distance down to the FWL can be estimated based on the pressure difference between the hydrocarbon phase and the water. However, the linear pressure decline during drainage has been seen in multiple experiments and is not yet properly understood.
- The early water production rate is limited by the probe conductivity, while at reduced water saturation the production become limited by the water relative permeability in the plug
- Experimental drainage history can be used for determination of primary drainage saturation curve and krw-tail. The production is not sensitive to kro or the upper part of the krw curve. Use of high conductivity discs allows more of the krw curve to be determined.
- The characteristic probe properties are: entry pressure, water volume, compressibility and conductivity.

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